

THE INFLUENCE OF FIBRE SURFACE TREATMENT
ON THE ADHESION OF CARBON FIBRES IN EPOXY RESIN

C.A.Baillie and M.G.Bader

Composite Materials Research Group

Department of Materials Science and Engineering

University of Surrey

Guildford, Surrey GU25XH

ABSTRACT

The adhesion of carbon fibres (electrolytically surface treated) to epoxy resin is investigated using two micromechanics tests. Fragmentation tests carried out on fibre treated at all levels show that average fragment lengths and hence the stress transfer length reduces with treatment indicating a more efficient bond. This increase in adhesion levels off at the treatment defined XA25. Pull-out tests on the same systems have been carried out and a work of fracture and a shear strength for the interface were calculated on the basis of two separate approaches to debonding. The first is based on a shear strength criterion and the second a fracture mechanics model. These showed similar trends with a plateau at the XA25 level. Single fibre strength tests analysed by Weibull distribution indicate that there are two maxima at the XA5 and XA25 levels. It is proposed that a weakly bonded layer is removed from the fibre during the early levels of treatment leaving a more stable layer for the resin to bond to.

KEYWORDS: Adhesion; Carbon Fibre; Surface Treatment; Interface; Pull-out.

1.INTRODUCTION

The properties of the composite depend on those of the fibre, matrix and the interface. Commercial treatments are applied to the surfaces of carbon fibres to promote adhesion in reinforced composites. There are several possible factors contributing to the bond between the fibre and the matrix. These may be mechanical factors including interlocking due to

microroughness - flaws, porosity etc on the fibre surface, physical effects of wetting and adsorption or finally chemical bonding between the two components (1). The aim of the present work is to comprehensively study one resin/fibre system in order to increase understanding of the mechanism of adhesion. To do this a fibre was taken in its untreated state and treated systematically by an electrolytic oxidation process. The treated fibres were then characterised and their behaviour in a single control epoxy resin evaluated.

The response at the interface to changes to the fibre surface is often measured using single fibre model tests (2). Fragmentation tests are used to measure an average shear strength along the interface. Pull-out tests on selected treatment levels enable more useful parameters to be determined. Two approaches to the debond problem in the pull-out test have been developed. One considers a maximum shear stress criterion and the other is based on fracture mechanics where debonding is treated as a fracture propagation. A recent example of each of these models (3,4,5) is used in this work to analyse the data and to determine values of a work of fracture of the interface and a shear strength.

Single fibre tensile tests at each treated fibre level are required in order to interpret the fragmentation tests. The data is fitted to a Weibull distribution as values of the strength of fibres at the fragment lengths are required. The results give additional information on flaw population and distribution.

2.EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Surface Treatment The high strength XA fibres were received untreated and unsized and in order to systematically increase the adhesive properties, they were oxidised by an anodic treatment based on the patent from Hercules (6). The specific charge applied controls the degree of improvement in adhesion. Fibres were treated at intervals up to 400 coulombs/m² (c/m²). The treatments will be referred to by their level of c/m² i.e. XA1 for XA fibre treated 1 c/m² (U=untreated).

2.2 Interface studies

2.2.1 Fragmentation This test involves embedding a single fibre in resin and applying tension until the fibre has fractured into many small fragments. The test is based on the assumption that when the last fracture has occurred, a distribution of the lengths should lie within the range $lc/2$ - lc . Kelly (7) proposed that this critical length, lc , was the minimum length of fibre required in order for the stress in the fibre to build up to fibre failure stress. Although only a very simple approximation of stress transfer, it does demonstrate the idea of

a "transfer length" very well.

Dogbone samples of single fibres in resin were manufactured. The resin used was a standard DGEBA type epoxy with amine hardener (triethylenetetramine). The fibres were aligned in a mould and the resin poured in after degassing. Samples were cured at 60°C for three hours followed by a post cure of 120°C for another three hours. After removal from the mould and polishing, samples were tested on a straining stage attached to an optical microscope. Transmitted, polarised light was used to view the fibres through the resin.

Cumulative distributions of fragment lengths from some of the tests carried out are shown in fig.1 and demonstrate a shift to shorter fragment lengths, with increase in treatment level. If the median value of the data for all fibres is read off at 50% on the cumulative distribution plot and plotted against surface treatment level then it can be observed that there is a levelling off at XA25. It appears that any treatment at higher levels is not significantly increasing the bond (see fig.2). Values of median length are shown in Table 1.

Using Kelly's model a value of shear strength of the interface, τ may be calculated from:

$$\tau = \sigma d / 2 lc$$

σ = strength, d = diameter, lc = 4/3 average fragment length

Although this may not be considered as a material parameter it may serve as a comparison of interface strengths from one fibre to another. The weak link model of Weibull (see section 2.3) can produce a value of strength for the fragment length. τ values for the treated and untreated fibres are shown in Table 1. They rise with treatment level to a plateau by XA15 -XA25. The values are of the same order as those calculated by Drzal(8) for AU untreated fibre (24MPa) and AS treated carbon fibre (74MPa).

2.2.2 Pull-out tests The pull-out test is based on an adaptation of the test developed by Sanchez and Desarmot at ONERA (9) by Pitkethly and Doble of the RAE (10). The fibre is guided into a pool of resin (same system of epoxy/amine as with the fragmentation tests) in the base of the holder (see fig.3). After curing, the specimen holder is fixed into a micromanipulator and the fibre led up into a tiny hole in a screw at the base of a soldering iron which is attached to a load cell on the tensile tester. Solder is applied to the screw head to hold the fibre in place. When the solder is solid the contraction of the soldering iron pulls the fibre out of the resin. The load required to do this is recorded. Embedded lengths are required for a full analysis of the pull-out load and they are measured by transferring the sample after the test to the S.E.M.. Pull-out tests were carried out on XAU, XA10, XA25 and XA50.

An example of the plot of maximum pull-out stress against embedded length is shown in fig.4 for XAU and XA25 and it can be seen that generally the values are higher for the treated fibre. Analysis of the plots are necessary in order to obtain meaningful physical parameters. Two approaches are considered. The energy approach is characterised by the assumption that the propagation of the debonding zone requires an energy which is characteristic of the bond. An example of this approach by Gao is shown fitted to the data in fig. 4. The stress criterion is based on the assumption that debonding takes place only when the maximum stress at the interface reaches a critical value.

A maximum shear stress approach by Hsueh (4,5) and a fracture mechanics approach by Gao et al (3) are critically compared in a recent paper (11) using some of the present data. Gao's model has now been applied to the present complete data base in order to determine a work of fracture for each treatment level tested. The model, which is described fully in reference 3, gives the following expression for the work of fracture G_{ic} :

$$\text{Pull-out or Maximum debond stress } \sigma_d = \sigma_o + \sigma - \sigma_o (1 - e^{-\lambda L})$$

$$\sigma_o = (4E_f G_{ic} / r (1 - 2kv_f))^{0.5}$$

σ is a function of radial stress from the resin, σ_o = frictionless debond stress, λ is related to the coefficient of friction. These and k are functions of v_m , v_f , E_m , E_f and the radius of the fibre and the resin surrounding it, r and R . L is the debond length.

As discussed in (11), Gao's model overestimates the debond stress, σ_d and therefore the pull-out stress for very short embedded lengths. Conversely, Hsueh's model is inaccurate for long lengths. His model states that:

$$\sigma_d = \sigma_o + (\sigma - \sigma_o)(1 - B_1/\lambda + B_2)$$

$$\sigma_o = 2\tau_b (1 + c/\beta r) \tanh \beta L$$

B_1, B_2 are functions of the debond length. These, c and β are related to v_m, v_f, E_m, E_f , and the two radii, r and R . τ_b = shear strength of the interface.

From this model, which is described more fully in reference 4 and 5, values of τ for the interface were calculated. These and the G_{ic} values from the Gao model are shown in Table 1 and demonstrate that the adhesion strength has reached a plateau with regard to surface treatment by XA25. The G_{ic} results for well treated fibre compare well with those of Piggott for treated carbon fibre - $30Jm^{-2}$ (12). The fits of both models to experimental data for XA25 fibre are shown in fig.5. and the weakness of Gao's model at low lengths is very apparent.

2.3 Single fibre strength tests In order to fully understand the mechanism of stress transfer and the study of interface adhesion it is necessary to investigate the effects of surface treatment on the fibre strength. It is also important to understand how the length of the fibre affects strength. Fibres were tested by the standard ASTM method (13) but using a multi window card of three gauge lengths, 12mm, 30mm and 75mm. The fibres were randomly selected from a tow of 12,000 and 40 samples of each gauge length tested for each of the following fibres: XAU, XA5, XA10, XA15, XA25, XA50 and XA100.

The stresses were calculated from the maximum load and from a value of the diameter for each fibre. These were determined using an image shearing method. Mean values of diameter are shown in Table 1. Fibre tensile strengths may be treated by a Weibull distribution function to investigate their dependence on length. The values of fibre strengths are ranked into ascending order and each one assigned a linearly distributed Pf (Probability of failure). An example of one cumulative frequency plot of these values for XA400 30mm gauge length is shown in fig.6.

The Weibull distribution is described below:

$$P_f = 1 - \exp(-(\sigma - \sigma_u / \sigma_o)^w)$$

σ = strength, σ_u = min.strength (0), σ_o = characteristic strength for pf = 0.368 and w = Weibull modulus.

This may be rearranged and a plot of $\ln \ln (1/1-P_f)$ against σ_o will give a straight line of gradient w. An example of one plot which fits the model well - XA400 30mm and one which seems to possess bimodal distribution - XA10 30mm can be seen in fig.7. Values of characteristic strength and an average Weibull modulus for each treatment level tested are shown in Table 1 and characteristic strengths for the fibres at all gauge lengths are shown in fig.8. The strength length relationship expected for an elastic brittle material is demonstrated for all fibres. Also it can be seen that the strengths and Weibull moduli peak at XA5 and XA25. XA100 has a high value of w - the reason for this is unclear.

3.DISCUSSION

Fragmentation and pull-out tests have indicated an improvement in adhesion strength up to XA25 after which no significant increase is noted. The treatment prepares the surface of the fibre for increased adhesion but may also alter the mechanism of adhesion completely. It is important to discover what it is that is causing the increase and the levelling of adhesion

strength by XA25.

The single fibre strength tests have demonstrated that the treatment affects the strength of the fibres. There is an initial increase in strength followed by a reduction and a subsequent rise to XA25. This is demonstrated at all three gauge lengths. If the proposal of Drzal(8) is correct, that a weakly bonded layer is removed by the treatment (not defect laden as he suggests) then it is considered that this happens before XA25. The strength peak at XA5 could be due to the loss of debris on the surface and the subsequent fall due to the layer of graphite peeling off like an onion skin. Guigon's model based on T.E.M. work demonstrates this structure with layers of graphite having a variable transverse radius of curvature that decreases from surface to centre (14). If the layer removal releases residual stress enabling more plane edges to unfold onto the surface to act as crack initiators, the strength will drop. Increased treatment must then smooth the surface.

Drzal's proposal for the removal of a weakly bonded layer was presented to explain the increase in adhesion by surface treatment. It can be seen that the freshly smoothed underlayer with its abundant edge sites for bonding would explain well the adhesion strength reaching its plateau value at XA25.

4.CONCLUSIONS

It has been demonstrated that electrolytic oxidation improves the adhesion of XA fibres to epoxy resin. Fragmentation and pull-out tests both indicate an increase in adhesion strength, whether shear strength or work of fracture. Single fibre tests have shown that there is an increase in the value of characteristic strength at the point of optimum adhesion. It has been proposed that a weakly bonded layer of graphite is removed by the treatment. This leaves a firm underlayer with plentiful edge sites for potential bonding.

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Table 1.

Surface Treatment	0	5	10	15	25	50	100
Fragment length (mm)	.93	.5	.48	.37	.35	.32	.3
Shear strength τ (MPa)	36	84	83	104	106	130	108
Pull-out τ_b (MPa)	43	-	57	-	66	66	66
Gic (Jm ⁻²)	7	-	17	-	27	27	26
σ_o 75mm (GPa)	3.6	4.4	3.8	3.3	3.8	3.6	3.6
σ_o 30mm (GPa)	3.6	4.7	4.1	4.1	4.5	4.5	3.9
σ_o 12mm (GPa)	5	5.1	5.1	4.3	5.2	4.7	4.9
Weibull modulus w	3.2	3.6	3.4	3.4	3.8	3.4	4.15
Diameter (μ m)	6.8	6.9	6.9	7.0	6.9	6.8	7.0

Fig.1. Cumulative distribution of fragment lengths for untreated and treated carbon fibres.

Fig.2. Median values of fragment lengths for untreated and treated fibres showing the decrease in length with increase in treatment.

Fig.3. Apparatus for the pull-out test showing sample preparation and adapted tensile tester.

Fig.4. Maximum debond stress of XAU and XA25 fibre plotted against embedded length to show the increase in stress with application of treatment.

Fig.5. Maximum debond stress values of XA25 fibre plotted against embedded length showing the fit to Gao (3) and Hsueh (4) models.

Fig.6. Cumulative distribution of strengths for XA400 fibre

Fig.7. Weibull plot for XA400 (30mm) and XA10 (30mm), the latter demonstrating bimodel behaviour.

Fig.8. Characteristic strengths of untreated and treated carbon fibres at three gauge lengths.